

Glyoxal-bis-isonicotinoylhydrazone as Analytical Reagent for Determination of Uranium(VI) and Iron(III)

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Glyoxal-bis-isonicotinoylhydrazone (GINH) has been found to be a suitable analytical reagent for spectrophotometric determination of uranium(vi) and iron(III).

Results and Discussion

The ethanolic solutions of GINH- U^{VI} and GINH- Fe^{III} complexes with Ringbom's optimum ranges of 3-10 ppm of U^{VI} or 2-8 ppm of Fe^{III} were found to remain stable for 72 and 24 h with maximum absorbances at 435 and 440 nm, and obeyed Beer's law upto 10 and 5 ppm respectively. The molar absorptivities, Sandell sensitivity¹ and dissociation constants of the U^{VI} and Fe^{III} complexes were found to be 16 190 and 6 053 $dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$, 15 and 9 $\mu g cm^{-2}$, 3.71×10^{-3} and 2.80×10^{-7} respectively.

It was found that for maximum complexation of 3.36×10^{-5} mole of uranium(VI) and 7.14×10^{-5} mole of iron(III) respectively, 1.0 and 0.6 ml of $1.70 \times 10^{-3} M$ reagent were necessary.

The molar compositions of the U^{VI} -GINH and Fe^{III} -GINH complexes were determined by Job's continuous variation method. They were found to be 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) for the U and Fe complexes respectively.

Effect of diverse ion : On the quantitative determination of U^{VI} and Fe^{III} with GINH, the effect of diverse ion were studied using separately 3.36×10^{-5} moles of U^{VI} and 8.82×10^{-5} moles of Fe^{III} with 1.69×10^{-4} and $3.38 \times 10^{-4} M$ solutions respectively, in a final volume of 10 ml of pH ~5 and with decision of tolerance limit as the quantities of the foreign ions which caused a deviation less than $\pm 2\%$ of the absorbance value of the respective pure complexes. The results are shown in Table 1.

Experimental

The reagent (GINH) was prepared by adding glyoxal (10 ml in 5 ml ethanol) to isonicotinic acid hydrazide (5 g in 180 ml of 1 : 1 ethanol-water)

TABLE 1-TOLERANCE LIMIT OF DIVERSE IONS

Metal ion	For U^{VI} ppm	For Fe^{III} ppm
Ba ^{II}	None	None
Co ^{II}	1000	500
Hg ^{II}	200	200
Be ^{II}	200	200
Bi ^{II}	5	1
Fe ^{II}	200	200
W ^{VI}	10	10
Te ^{IV}	10	10
Mg ^{II}	1000	100
Mn ^{II}	None	100
Cd ^{II}	None	None
Zn ^{II}	400	200
Cu ^{II}	1	1
Acetate	30	100
Thiosulphate	50	1

while stirring continuously and allowing to stand for 72 h. The resulting solid was washed with alcohol, crystallised and dried at room temperature, m.p. 180°d. The reagent was found soluble in water in presence of 2 N HCl. Ethanolic solution of the reagent was used.

pH and spectral measurements of the solution were performed respectively with a Philips pH (94054) and a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer (Spekol) using 10 mm glass cells.

General procedure : To an aliquot of uranium(VI) upto 10 ppm of U^{VI} as hydrated uranyl nitrate²) or iron(III) (upto 5 ppm of Fe^{III} as $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$), the reagent solution (2 ml; $1.7 \times 10^{-3} M$) and buffer solution (1 ml; CH_3COONa/CH_3COOH) of pH 4.5 (for U and 5.0 for Fe) were added

and the resulting orange yellow complex (for both) was dissolved in ethanol and the solution was diluted to 10 ml with the same solvent. The absorbance of these solutions were measured against reagent blank.

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References

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